
FORMATION OF SKILLS FOR TEACHING TALENTED AND GIFTED CHILDREN TO BIOLOGISTS

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Abstract

Experience of mastering of innovative technologies of educating is examined In the article, That it is very necessary for mobilization. To the activity creatively, examining it, a business man is a characteristic of certain personality. Therefore we decided innovative technologies of one educating module themes. Educating of talented and gifted children is forming of future teachers, specialists in a flow it consciously. Development of children on the basis of inclusive education, т. of e. method of exposure talented and gifted students at ideas and researches.

Keywords: educational process, research, new system of education, innovative technology

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It is necessary to always remember the words of N. A. Nazarbayev: "the future of our country is in the hands of the younger generation, and the fate of the younger generation is in the hands of teachers."

The high development of any country depends on the high creative and rapid strength of the youth growing in them. Kindergartens, schools and other educational institutions are responsible for the upbringing of children, their comprehensive education.

The main support of any state is educated and qualified, business and active people. Therefore, as you know, the most important issue is the education of young people who, in accordance with the requirements of society, improve and develop society. The Law of the Republic of Kazakhstan "On Education" for the first time on the basis of state policy introduced such topical issues as "the intellectual development of each child in accordance with his individual abilities, the development of personal talents."

These problems can be seen in the works of scientists Francis Galton (19g), German educational psychologist E. Meiman (late 19g-early 20g), German psychologist V. Stern (1st half of the 20th century), D. J. Guilford, P. Torrens, F. Barren, K. Taylor.

Currently, a new education system has been developed in a sovereign country aimed at penetrating the world educational space. This is due to significant changes in the educational process. This is due to the fact that the paradigm of education has changed, the content of education is being updated, a new approach and new relationships are emerging. One of the

important issues is the mastery by teachers of the scientific and pedagogical foundations of innovative activities in education and education that meet the requirements of society.

In the era of accelerated development of science and technology, increasing the flow of information data, the main task of educational institutions is the formation of mental abilities, the development of human abilities and talents. It will come with the fruits of the tireless curiosity and creativity of the student, who needs to be updated like the air in the modern educational space. Therefore, depending on the abilities of each student, a big turn should be made to master the updated pedagogical technologies that carry out education, nurturing his independence, curiosity, creativity. After all, the organization of the educational process at the level of the state educational standard obliges to introduce new pedagogical technologies [1].

By constantly identifying talent or abilities, school teachers should position themselves as "gifted observers." The content side of this concept may be different. Children themselves can express themselves not only in one subject, but also in several subjects or other areas. For example: artistry, sports, music and other talents can be recognized. In addition, they may have problems in other areas if they are talented in one area. Although they are very capable at one stage of development, they may also not show their abilities in the following stages. These talents and abilities can be acquired by teachers, parents, and children themselves can determine. It is necessary to create conditions at school for the development of children's abilities. I think our school has created conditions for such children. Because the school has several sports clubs, subject electives, dance groups have been organized since the age of five, and many students participate in the choir. I believe that the main goal of the development of a gifted student is to increase the talent and abilities of the individual to a higher level.

At the school, gifted and talented students are observed during events organized in accordance with the work plan. To identify gifted, talented children, the following requirements are imposed: the development of an identification program, the use of new pedagogical technologies, monitoring the correct quality of the task given to the student, active participation in events, communication with parents- you have to be in a relationship. All teachers strive to create a favorable environment for children to achieve maximum success in education. In the case of gifted and talented children, this rather complex issue requires reflection, discussion and careful planning. A high school student can show exceptional talent in one particular subject and not stand out in other subjects. The range of outstanding abilities in special disciplines can be very extensive. And also the ability to build trusting relationships. A student who is used to creative work in the classroom will be inclined to what kind of creative work in high school. They are trying to solve problems on their own with a new idea. As a result, society's need to meet the needs of gifted people sets the task of the education system to pave the way for the development of personal abilities and social activity of the child, the formation of a creative personality. When identifying and working with gifted children, we must pay special attention to the pedagogical, psychiatric, and social state of the environment in which this child is located. The environment that affects the child: parents, teacher, school, fellow public. In the process of work, we must carefully monitor the child's contacts with these environments. Special questionnaires are created for this purpose. The results of working with gifted children reach such an extent that the student can independently, independently assimilate knowledge. Work with gifted and talented children can be divided into the following stages. The control of a child's abilities, the determination of general giftedness, and development require special skill. You can't rush to control. That is, for

a teacher, understanding a child's soul is a great art. Freeman (1998) showed reliable criteria for determining the best students.

The new innovative technology of training is a special type of professional activity. To master the innovative technology of teaching, it is necessary to use a huge pedagogical experience. This is a job that requires a person who is creative about his activities, has certain business qualities of a person. In fact, the teacher develops and shapes himself in the process of mastering a new innovative technology. Let's focus on one of the modules of innovative learning technology mentioned above. He believes that teaching talented and gifted children is a conscious formation of future biologists, i.e. the creation of ideas and research to identify children based on an inclusive approach to the development of education of talented and gifted students. A teacher who knows how to determine the abilities of students in a timely manner also knows future talents. Therefore, we have instructed future biology teachers who will be able to distinguish between these gifted and talented students to conduct a survey of schoolchildren, suggesting research methods.

A student may show exceptional giftedness in one particular subject and not stand out in other subjects. With unidentified children, the school psychologist conducts various trainings, gives relevant questionnaire questions and determines the definition. I believe that the work plan with gifted children can be organized as follows: identifying gifted children, promoting creative self-improvement of gifted children, monitoring the development of cognitive activity of gifted students, rewarding gifted children, working with parents of gifted children, working with teachers, interacting with other school societies in order to create favorable conditions for the development of giftedness.

It should be remembered that gifted and talented students are not a homogeneous group, each of them has a special property. However, when considering the category of gifted and talented students in a group setting, a number of common characteristics can be seen. Some students can demonstrate the presence of such qualities in a number of areas, while others – only in one area. In most gifted students, this behavior may be more noticeable and intense. Talented and talented students are always impossible to find immediately by their behavior, since sometimes their exceptional abilities do not even manifest themselves. The giftedness of some students may not even manifest itself under the influence of objective reasons, otherwise they probably have not had the opportunity to show their abilities yet. And the rest may fall into the category of those who do not have time for various reasons, or deliberately hide their talent. Now some gifted and talented students may face learning difficulties that will hinder the manifestation of their true abilities.

Gifted and talented students have broad field abilities: some of them, for example, may demonstrate exceptional abilities in the field of science and technology, and some may manifest themselves in art or poetry, in public leadership. Currently, gifted and talented students are determined not only by the presence of high intelligence. The system of principles concerning the concept of giftedness and talent includes a wide range of general intellectual, academic abilities, creative, leadership abilities, individual capabilities and visual and performing abilities in art. They may also have difficulties in other areas if they are talented in one area; they may not show their abilities in the next stages if they are very capable at one stage of development. These talents and abilities can be determined by teachers, parents, other group members, or the children themselves. It is necessary to create conditions for children to demonstrate their abilities, qualifications, and potential, and this can be very difficult for them at an early age.

Today, starting from elementary school, we must pay great attention to what affects the development of a student's speech. This is because a student with a good language can achieve good results anywhere. And a student who does not speak the language cannot express what he knows to his degree. One aspect of the fact that a student experiences such difficulties is that in elementary school, the skill of minute learning is widely used to form speed reading skills in children. During this period of primary school, it is important to monitor the understanding and learning, as well as the formation of the child for rapid learning. This is because the student, without understanding or reading the text, for some reason reads the dry text too quickly, which leads to a big mistake. Later, as they move into high school, the student's reading comprehension skills gradually decrease. It follows from this that some students memorize the content of any text or story. In this regard, "the earlier attention is paid to the development of the child's abilities and talents, the more chances there are for his full disclosure," American scientists say.

Therefore, it is impossible to rush to determine the giftedness of a child as a whole. To do this, we use well-known pedagogical and psychological methods to determine the specific qualities of a young person. Confidentiality is respected when studying and individualizing a student. Reason: if a child is upset, his existing abilities do not grow, but may disappear.

In the traditional educational process, teachers generally do not have enough time for creativity. At the same time, since a gifted child is inclined to enjoy his work, the method of memorization and repetition makes him, firstly, quickly boring, and secondly, the illusion of "full assimilation of knowledge" arises in his mind, that is, "full knowledge of the didactic material that takes place in the lesson", in-third, he does not tolerate dependence on the teacher. As a result, talent fades. In order for giftedness not to fade away, the child must be under constant control, constantly act on a creative level, not feel dependent on the teacher. Each student should know that his teacher is in a research facility, and his classmates should not know each other, observation should be carried out naturally.

McAlpine and Reed (1996) compiled and presented a useful list of the behavior of gifted and talented students. In fact, no gifted student has all of these characteristics: they may have all or achieve all of the characteristics in one category, but they may be a little "lame" in another. In this section, the concepts of "gifted" and "talented" were combined into "gifted and talented". However, some researchers argue that they need to be differentiated, claiming that they are different. In the case of differentiation of giftedness categories, this is due to a higher level of intelligence or abilities, and talent is associated with a higher level in the field of music, art, various crafts, dance or sports, etc. Some researchers consider the importance of self-control in two categories: how many talents, however, in their opinion, to abilities (intelligence, creativity, social affectivity, etc.), and talents are considered more achievements in various fields (scientific, technical, artistic, personal, sports, etc.). Talent is sometimes associated with perfection and great achievements, but sometimes it remains owned by only a small number of competent entities.

- Currently, there is a tendency to move away from considering the gifted and gifted within the framework of mono-aspect (for example, with a high IQ) in favor of multispectability, which involves a wide range of unique abilities.

- Cultural values that determine participation in abilities and qualities are an important component of any concept of talent and talent.

- The definition of the procedure and content of the program should cover an equal degree of multicultural perspective.

- Social, emotional and stimulating factors are considered in terms of the most important aspects of talent and talent.

- Behavioral characteristics such as interest in learning and language skills, as well as abstract thinking skills, a high level of knowledge, thirst for knowledge and enthusiasm will be very useful when searching for talented and talented students [2].

To date, education that satisfies the abilities of gifted children at a high level is developing in many civilized countries on the basis of the principle of differentiated education. It is conducted at a modern level in the education system of France, America, Germany, England, Japan, etc.

Speaking at the II Republican Congress of Education and Science Workers, the President noted that one of the tasks facing general education today is "special attention to the development of schools working with gifted children", which will contribute to the further development of Kazakhstan. Speaking at the II Republican Congress of Education and Science Workers, the President noted that one of the tasks facing general education today is "special attention to the development of schools working with gifted children", which will contribute to the further development of Kazakhstan.

At the same time, the modern stage of development of our society poses the problem of technologization of the process of teaching gifted children to the school education system. At the same time, the modern stage of development of our society poses the problem of technologization of the process of teaching gifted children to the school education system.

According to such requests, various teaching technologies are being developed and introduced into school practice. For example: the technology of academician V. I. Monokhov, the method of collective learning V. K. Dyachenko, the model technology of teaching M. M. Zhanpeisova and the informatization of the education system of Professor Zh. A. Karaev, contributing to the deep individualization of the entire educational process of students, awakening a sense of independence, opening the way to the demand for talent, oriented technologies can be identified. The value of Karaev's technology :

- 1) 100% academic performance,
- 2) allows you to select a gifted child by completing high-level tasks;
- 3) the student is not afraid that he will get a "2", but on the contrary, increases motivation by gaining high scores for answering the task. The student is given a level 4 task;
- 4) the student independently masters the educational material, and the teacher compiles a workbook on his subject;
- 5) pedagogical technology is conducted in compliance with the principle of informatization of the secondary school system.

Thus, the inability to understand in its essence such psychological concepts as abilities, knowledge, skills, dexterity in the educational process, can expose teachers to pedagogical threats. The teacher should be able to navigate the characteristics of the student. It is even better if the teacher has one personal creative success. For example: performing, artistic, or

musical [3]. In working with gifted children, the teacher must hone his versatility, that is, the ability to be gifted in combination with knowledge and art.

References

1. «Qazahstan-2050» strategyasi qalipasqan memlekettin jana sayasi bagiti // Ontustik Qazakstan. – 2012, jeltoksan – 15. №198-199. – p. 8.
2. Begalieva R.N., Issayev G.I., Ergubekova J.S.// Okitudin innovatsiyalik aspektleri. Shimkent – 2017, p. 57.
3. Issayev G.I., Halikova G.S., Alpamisova G.B. // Biologiyani okitu adistemesi. Shimkent – 2017,